

CEN and CENELEC

RISERS PROJECT

“Roadmap for Industrial Symbiosis Standardisation for Efficient Resource Sharing”

IP Form

The project “A Roadmap for Industrial Symbiosis Standardisation for Efficient Resource Sharing” (the “**RISERS Project**”, Grant Agreement ID 101135539) is dedicated to guiding the standardisation of industrial symbiosis to enhance resource efficiency across Europe. Funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Programme, RISERS aims to address standardisation gaps and overcome barriers hindering efficient resource sharing. The organisation of the roadmap (Work Package 6 and 7) is led by CEN and CENELEC.

By signing this participant registration, you accept the following conditions:

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You agree to offer your expertise in the drafting process, and to contribute by electronic contributions or by participation in meetings to this process.

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Organization name	Click or tap here to enter text.
Street/Street Number	Click or tap here to enter text.
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Town/City	Click or tap here to enter text.
Country	Click or tap here to enter text.

2. Name and contact details of the individual participant(s) representing your organization:
(It is possible to register several participants)

Participant 1:

Title	Click or tap here to enter text.
Last Name	Click or tap here to enter text.
First Name	Click or tap here to enter text.
Function	Click or tap here to enter text.
Telephone	Click or tap here to enter text.
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I have read and agree with the above conditions, and I wish to register myself and my organization as participant in the RISERS Project.

Date: Click or tap here to enter text.

Signature:

Participant 2 (optional):

Title	Click or tap here to enter text.
Last Name	Click or tap here to enter text.
First Name	Click or tap here to enter text.
Function	Click or tap here to enter text.
Telephone	Click or tap here to enter text.
E-mail	Click or tap here to enter text.

I have read and agree with the above conditions, and I wish to register myself and my organization as participant in the RISERS Project.

Date: Click or tap here to enter text.

Signature:

3. Name and contact details of your organization's representative:

Title	Click or tap here to enter text.
Last Name	Click or tap here to enter text.
First Name	Click or tap here to enter text.
Function	Click or tap here to enter text.
Telephone	Click or tap here to enter text.
E-mail	Click or tap here to enter text.

I have read and agree with the above conditions, and I wish to register my organization as a participant in the RISERS Project.

Date: Click or tap here to enter text.

Signature:
